

Gaze as an Implicit Second Authentication Factor when using PIN Mechanisms in Extended Reality

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Recent advances in extended reality (XR) have enabled seamless access to immersive services. However, user authentication in these environments typically relies on conventional methods, such as PIN entry, which remains vulnerable to unauthorized use. This paper investigates gaze behavior as an implicit second authentication factor in XR. Using a Meta Quest Pro headset, participants performed legitimate and impostor login attempts while their gaze data were recorded. Temporal, spatial, and oculomotor metrics revealed distinctive and reproducible gaze dynamics between user roles. Tree-based machine learning models, particularly XGBoost, reliably distinguished legitimate from impostor sessions under user-independent validation (AUC = .84). Calibrating model thresholds further enabled adaptive balancing between security and usability. These findings demonstrate that gaze dynamics can unobtrusively enhance PIN authentication, introducing an adaptive layer that aligns authentication sensitivity with situational risk and user needs in immersive environments.

CCS Concepts: • **Human-centered computing** → **Mixed / augmented reality**; *Empirical studies in HCI*; • **Security and privacy** → **Usability in security and privacy**; *Authentication*; • **Computing methodologies** → *Machine learning approaches*.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: gaze behavior, implicit authentication, usable security, extended reality (XR), eye tracking, behavioral biometrics, human-centered authentication, adaptive security, privacy-preserving interaction

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1 Introduction

Extended Reality (XR) technologies are transforming how users interact with digital systems, enabling immersive access to communication, entertainment, and professional services. As these environments become integrated into everyday life, securing access to personal and sensitive information is crucial. However, most XR applications rely on conventional authentication methods, such as Personal Identification Numbers (PINs), initially designed for flat-screen and mobile contexts. Although these methods are familiar and cognitively simple, they remain vulnerable to unauthorized use.

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Previous research has primarily aimed to improve XR authentication by leveraging new modalities (e.g., gesture-, gaze-, and motion-based modalities) that resist observation attacks (e.g., [Mathis et al. 2021]). Although these approaches enhance security, they often reduce usability by introducing unfamiliar interaction demands that disrupt the fluid and embodied nature of XR experiences. Rather than replacing established mechanisms, an alternative is to augment them with implicit behavioral factors that strengthen security while balancing usability.

This work follows that path and focuses on unauthorized access during PIN authentication. We investigate whether gaze behavior, captured passively through integrated eye tracking, can serve as an implicit second factor during PIN authentication in XR. The central assumption is that legitimate users and impostors, even when entering the same PIN, exhibit distinct gaze patterns reflecting differences in attention, familiarity, and cognitive load. Instead of identifying users directly, the proposed approach detects anomalies in gaze behavior to reveal potentially unauthorized access attempts. We examine this hypothesis through three complementary research questions: (i) RQ_1 Do legitimate users and impostors exhibit distinct gaze behaviors during PIN entry in XR? (ii) RQ_2 Can machine learning models distinguish between legitimate and impostor sessions based on gaze features under user-independent conditions? (iii) RQ_3 How can the resulting model be calibrated to balance security and usability under realistic operational scenarios?

By addressing these questions, our work provides empirical and practical insights into authentication in XR, reframing gaze not as a standalone biometric but as an unobtrusive enhancement to familiar mechanisms, thereby strengthening security without compromising user experience. The study makes three main contributions: (i) it provides empirical evidence that gaze dynamics, especially spatial efficiency and dwell-time patterns, distinguish legitimate users from impostors; (ii) it shows that ensemble-based models can detect anomalous authentication attempts without explicit user effort; and (iii) it introduces an adaptive calibration framework that allows stakeholders to adjust model sensitivity to balance security and usability according to contextual risk.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 discusses related work and research objective; Sections 3–5 present the methodology, analyses, and findings for each research question; Section 6 discusses implications, limitations, and directions for future research.

2 Related work and research objective

2.1 Related work

2.1.1 User authentication in XR. Based on the authentication factors, authentication can be categorized as knowledge-, possession-, or inheritance-based. Knowledge-based mechanisms are the most explored, mainly due to their familiarity and ease of implementation. Examples include PIN-based systems [Abdelrahman et al. 2022; Zhang et al. 2017], graphical passwords requiring recall or recognition [Düzgün et al. 2022; Hadjidemetriou et al. 2019], and gesture-based secrets [Islam et al. 2018; Ragozin et al. 2022]. Although flexible, they often suffer from input imprecision, cognitive load, and vulnerability to observation attacks unless mitigated through dynamic cues or randomized layouts [Mathis et al. 2021; Winkler et al. 2015]. Possession-based mechanisms are limited, with few studies using one-time passwords or QR code scanning via headsets [Chan et al. 2015; Latvala et al. 2018]. While effective against phishing and shoulder-surfing, they depend on external hardware and disrupt immersion, reducing their practicality. Inheritance-based mechanisms leverage physiological or behavioral biometrics, with the former (e.g., iris or pupil features) providing strong distinctiveness but being limited by environmental and hardware factors [Boutros et al. 2020; Yan et al. 2020], and the latter (e.g., gaze, head, or gait patterns) enabling continuous implicit authentication yet being susceptible to variability [Lohr and Komogortsev 2022; Shen et al. 2019].

2.1.2 PIN authentication in XR. PINs remain among the most widely used authentication methods due to their simplicity and familiarity. Despite their high usability, PIN mechanisms face notable security challenges, specifically vulnerability to observation attacks and unauthorized access. Research has mainly focused on mitigating observation attacks by adjusting PIN mechanisms to implement novel techniques, including keypad shifting and redirection [Weiss et al. 2024], cue-based entry methods [Abdelrahman et al. 2022], 3D manipulation [Mathis et al. 2021], and integration of gesture-, voice-, and touch-based input modalities [Li et al. 2020; Yadav et al. 2015]. While these methods enhance resistance to observation attacks, they often reduce overall usability, compared to original PIN entry methods [Riyadh et al. 2024].

2.1.3 Unauthorized access. Unauthorized access is a constant weakness of PIN-based authentication. Since access depends only on entering the correct code, anyone who knows the PIN can log in as the legitimate user. Because the mechanism verifies the secret rather than the individual, it cannot distinguish between authorized and unauthorized users, allowing intrusions to occur and compromising overall system security. To address this issue, researchers have proposed various approaches, including explicit integration with complementary mechanisms [Kausar et al. 2022], redesigned PIN layouts [Guerar et al. 2020], and context-dependent schemes relying on trusted devices or locations [Cho et al. 2021]. However, these approaches often reduce overall usability, depend on explicit user actions, or require external contextual factors.

2.1.4 The role of gaze in authentication. Gaze has been employed in three main ways: explicit and implicit gaze-based authentication and gaze-supported multi-factor authentication [Katsini et al. 2020]. Focusing on implicit authentication, this approach leverages unconscious eye movement patterns to verify user identity without requiring explicit user input, using diverse eye-tracking metrics and both controlled and continuous visual stimuli, with the latter enabling unobtrusive authentication during everyday tasks such as reading or browsing. In XR, gaze has been used for identifying users through gaze and head movement patterns that form distinctive and reproducible behavioral movements suitable for unobtrusive authentication [Liebers et al. 2021], leveraging natural gaze behavior during everyday virtual interactions [Lohr et al. 2024], through lightweight and generalizable deep learning models [Lohr and Komogortsev 2022]. However, these approaches rely on user identification models, whose performance may vary depending on contextual conditions, temporal stability, and population size, especially as the number of users and interaction scenarios increases.

2.2 Research objective and questions

Following the analysis of the related work, this paper aims to examine whether gaze can be used not as a direct authentication factor but as an additional implicit indicator for detecting potential unauthorized access attempts. In other words, to explore whether gaze behavior can serve as an implicit second authentication factor that enhances the security of a widely used and highly usable mechanism (i.e., PIN) against unauthorized access, considering that gaze-based behavioral cues may reveal differences between legitimate users and impostors, reflecting deviations in visual attention, decision-making, and spatial search dynamics during the authentication process. To explore this hypothesis, we structured our paper around three complementary research questions (RQs):

RQ₁ *Do legitimate users and impostors exhibit different gaze behaviors during PIN authentication in XR?* RQ₁ establishes the behavioral foundation of our work and aims to determine whether observable visual patterns differ systematically between legitimate and impostor sessions by analyzing temporal, spatial, and entropy-based gaze metrics; the outcomes of RQ₁ provide

evidence of behavioral separability, which motivates the use of gaze features for classification (RQ_2).

- RQ_2 *Can machine learning models identify legitimate and impostor attempts based on gaze features in PIN authentication in XR?* Building on the behavioral findings of RQ_1 , RQ_2 evaluates several classification models, aiming to quantify the power of gaze metrics, identify the most robust model families, and examine their operational trade-offs between security (impostor detection) and usability (legitimate acceptance).
- RQ_3 *How can the top-performing model be calibrated to balance security and usability under realistic operational conditions?* RQ_3 extends beyond classification accuracy, focusing on threshold calibration and operational decision trade-offs. By leveraging the top-performing model from RQ_2 , we analyze how different decision thresholds translate into adaptive system responses to balance user convenience and system security.

3 RQ1 – Gaze-based differences between legitimate users and impostors

3.1 Methodology

3.1.1 Participants. Seventy-two individuals participated in the study (52 self-identified as men, 20 as women), with ages ranging from 19 to 51 years ($M = 22$, $SD = 6$). The built-in eye tracker of the headset functioned reliably for all participants, including those wearing prescription glasses or contact lenses; no participants were excluded for technical reasons. In terms of prior experience, the majority reported low to medium familiarity with XR technologies ($n = 40$) and nearly all participants had frequent experience with PIN-based authentication ($n = 70$).

3.1.2 Apparatus. The study was conducted using a *Meta Quest Pro* headset with its integrated binocular eye tracker, with a reported accuracy of $\pm 0.5^\circ - 1.1^\circ$ (depending on calibration and viewing angle). The headset provides stereoscopic displays with a resolution of 1800×1920 pixels per eye, a refresh rate of 90 Hz, and a field of view of $\approx 106^\circ$ (horizontal) $\times 96^\circ$ (vertical). The PIN mechanism was developed in Unity 2022.3 using the Meta XR All-in-One SDK (v72) and Meta XR Interaction SDK (v72) with XR Plugin Management (v4.4). Gaze data were obtained via the Meta XR Movement SDK (Combined Gaze estimate) and logged as timestamped 3D gaze intersection points. Based on the recorded logs, the effective eye-tracking sampling frequency was 72 Hz under the runtime configuration used in this study.

3.1.3 PIN mechanism. The interface was implemented as a world-anchored floating canvas rendered in VR against a uniform black background. The keypad followed a fixed 3×3 grid layout with a bottom row containing the digit “0” delete key for erasing the last digit, symmetrically arranged with uniform spacing following common practice (e.g., [Abdelrahman et al. \[2022\]](#)). A masked input field was positioned at the top of the panel to display entered digits. Interaction followed a gaze-and-trigger paradigm: participants fixated on a digit, which became visually highlighted upon gaze contact, and confirmed their selection using a handheld controller trigger (e.g., similar to [Mathis et al. 2021](#)). No raycasting beam was employed. The spatial configuration of the interface remained constant across all trials. Areas of Interest (AOIs) corresponded to the rectangular bounds of each digit button; gaze samples were assigned to an AOI when the eye-tracking ray intersected the corresponding button collider. Fig. 1a provides a schematic representation of the interface, including all relevant distances and element dimensions.

3.1.4 Gaze metrics. They were grouped into six complementary behavioral categories reflecting distinct aspects of visual attention and search behavior during login (Table 1). To derive them, we applied a dispersion-threshold identification algorithm to timestamped 3D gaze intersection points (72 Hz, Meta Quest Pro Combined Gaze). A 120 ms sliding window was used, consistent

with common I-DT duration thresholds [Elshamy and Khooshabeh 2021]; spatial dispersion was defined as the maximum Euclidean distance between any gaze sample and the window centroid. A fixation was detected when dispersion remained below a fixed threshold ($D_{\text{thr}} = 35$, ≈ 3.5 cm at a 2 m viewing distance, $\approx 1^\circ$ of visual angle), for at least 120 ms; the window was expanded until violation. Invalid samples terminated segments. Saccades were defined as inter-fixation intervals; amplitude was computed as the Euclidean distance between successive fixation endpoints, and scanpath length as cumulative Euclidean displacement per trial. All parameters were fixed across participants. Sensitivity analysis ($\pm 20\%$ variation of D_{thr}) confirmed robustness of the reported effects. No additional temporal smoothing or post-processing was applied; binocular fusion was handled by the Meta XR Movement SDK.

3.1.5 Procedure.

- **Recruitment and registration:** We issued an open call for participation through announcements and social media, directing interested individuals to a dedicated study webpage. From there, participants could review detailed study information and, if willing to join, select a convenient time slot. Upon registration, participants provided their informed consent and were free to withdraw at any time without penalty. Participation was voluntary and no monetary compensation was provided. The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical review procedures and requirements of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki.
- **Lab session:** At the study venue, a researcher provided an overview of the process, answered questions, and clarified potential concerns before proceeding. Next, participants wore the headset and performed the standard Meta Quest Pro eye-tracking calibration procedure, followed by a familiarization task designed to introduce them to the modalities used in the main experiment. The main experiment consisted of two phases: (i) each participant created a personal six-digit PIN to secure a simulated account and performed several login sessions using this PIN; these sessions represented legitimate user interactions; and (ii) participants were given PINs created by others and instructed to use these PINs to attempt access to alternative accounts; these sessions simulated impostor login attempts. For impostor sessions, the researcher presented the assigned PIN outside the XR environment on a printed sheet and read it aloud, allowing a 10-second memorization period, and explicitly instructed participants not to write the PIN down or retain any external reference. Before the session, the researcher asked participants to recall the PIN to confirm correct memorization verbally; if recall was incorrect, the researcher re-presented the PIN and repeated the check. During the login session, we provided no visual or auditory cues about the PIN. On average, participants completed 16 legitimate login sessions using their own PIN ($SD = 3$) and 6 impostor sessions using PINs assigned by other participants ($SD = 2$), resulting in an overall legitimate-to-impostor ratio of approximately 3:1 across the dataset. During each login attempt, the headset's integrated sensors continuously captured and stored gaze data corresponding to the participant's visual behavior during PIN entry.
- **Analysis** After completing all sessions, we collected and analyzed gaze data through a three-step process, aiming to (i) examine gaze-based differences between legitimate and impostor sessions, (ii) select the top-performing classification models under user-independent validation, and (iii) calibrate thresholds to balance security and usability. In total, we analyzed 1613 login sessions.

3.1.6 Statistical analysis. We tested whether legitimate and impostor sessions differed in gaze behavior using two complementary analyses that account for the unbalanced, clustered structure of the data: (i) for each gaze metric, we fitted a linear mixed-effects model with role (impostor vs.

Table 1. Gaze metrics capturing complementary aspects of visual attention, temporal dynamics, and spatial search efficiency.

Category	Metric	Description and interpretation
Temporal	mean_dwell_time	Mean time the gaze remained on a single AOI (PIN digit); longer dwell times indicate slower or more effortful verification.
	std_dwell_time	Variability of dwell times across AOIs; higher values reflect inconsistent attention allocation or fluctuating search confidence.
Fixation-based	fixation_count	Total number of fixations during login; more fixations imply greater exploratory effort or uncertainty.
	mean_fixation_duration	Average fixation duration; longer fixations suggest deeper visual processing or difficulty identifying targets.
Saccade-based	mean_saccade_amplitude	Average Euclidean distance between consecutive fixation centroids; larger values indicate broader spatial shifts.
	mean_saccade_velocity	Mean transition velocity; lower velocities indicate cautious, deliberate exploration; higher velocities reflect faster search behavior.
Spatial	scanpath_length	Total distance traveled by gaze; longer paths indicate less efficient or more redundant visual exploration.
	gaze_efficiency	Ratio of straight-line distance between first and last fixation on targets to total scanpath length; values near 1 reflect direct and spatially optimal gaze paths.
Entropy-based	aoi_entropy_bits	Shannon entropy of AOI visit frequencies; high values denote evenly distributed, non-focused attention.
	transition_entropy_bits	Entropy of gaze transitions between AOIs; it captures the unpredictability and structure of gaze sequences.
	revisit_rate	Proportion of fixations returning to previously visited AOIs; higher rates indicate verification behavior or uncertainty.
General	num_unique_AOIs	Number of distinct AOIs fixated during login; reflects the breadth of visual coverage or target scanning.

legitimate) as a fixed effect, a random intercept for each legitimate user to account for repeated

Table 2. Summary of statistically significant and marginal effects across analyses for RQ_1 (FDR-corrected).

Metric	Mixed Model	Paired	Permutation	Interpretation
gaze_efficiency	–	.029	.012	Impostors show lower efficiency (less direct fixations)
mean_dwell_time	–	–	.048	Impostors dwell longer on PIN areas
std_dwell_time	–	–	.056	Slightly greater variability for impostors
All others	>.591	>.109	>.116	No systematic role effect

sessions, and an additional variance-component random intercept for each user to capture crossed clustering. Right-skewed metrics were log-transformed $\log(1 + x)$ when skewness exceeded 1.0; we report the fixed-effect estimate, 95% confidence intervals, and associated p-values; (ii) we performed a per-user paired comparison as a sensitivity analysis to equalize the influence across legitimate users; for each legitimate user, we averaged all legitimate sessions and all impostor sessions targeting that user, and compared the two means using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test across legitimate users. To control for multiple testing across gaze metrics, we applied the Benjamini-Hochberg False Discovery Rate (FDR) correction ($\alpha = .05$) separately to the mixed-effects and paired test p-values. These analyses estimate the overall role effect while: (i) accounting for repeated and unequal numbers of sessions per legitimate user and impostor, and (ii) providing a user-balanced, nonparametric corroboration of the findings.

3.2 Results

Linear mixed-effects models revealed no statistically significant fixed effects after Benjamini-Hochberg FDR correction ($p_{\text{FDR}} > 0.59$ for all metrics), suggesting considerable inter-individual variability in gaze behavior and an absence of consistent population-level differences when accounting for the crossed, repeated-measures structure. Descriptive inspection showed small, consistent tendencies for impostor sessions to exhibit longer dwell times and more variable fixation patterns. The per-user paired analysis further confirmed these tendencies, revealing a significant reduction in **gaze efficiency** for impostor sessions ($p_{\text{FDR}} = .029$), indicating less spatially direct visual trajectories toward target digits. Cluster-aware permutation tests strengthened this finding, showing significant effects for **gaze efficiency** ($p_{\text{FDR}} = .012$) and **mean dwell time** ($p_{\text{FDR}} = .048$), and a marginal effect for **dwell-time standard deviation** ($p_{\text{FDR}} = .056$). On average, impostor sessions demonstrated lower gaze efficiency ($M_{\text{legit}} = .743$, $M_{\text{impostor}} = .681$) and longer dwell times ($M_{\text{legit}} = 2.178$ s, $M_{\text{impostor}} = 4.091$ s), with small-to-medium standardized effects ($d = 0.323$ – 0.502). Although effect sizes are modest, this is expected under a stringent threat model in which impostors enter the correct PIN. In such settings, even small but consistent behavioral deviations can constitute reliable group-level differences when aggregated across sessions. Table 2 presents a summary of the statistically significant and marginal effects for RQ_1 .

Finding 1: Gaze efficiency and temporal attention distinguish legitimate from impostor logins

Impostor sessions showed longer dwell times and lower gaze efficiency across all analyses. Longer dwell times reflect a slower and more deliberate visual search process, while reduced

gaze efficiency indicates that impostors' scanpaths were less spatially direct and less optimal for reaching target digits. Hence, impostors engage in more hesitant, corrective, and inefficient visual exploration, consistent with increased cognitive uncertainty during PIN entry.

4 RQ2 – Model selection and refinement

4.1 Methodology

To address RQ_2 , we framed the task as a supervised binary classification problem in which each login session was represented by the gaze metrics derived in RQ_1 (Table 1) and labeled as either legitimate or impostor. In total, we evaluated 1613 login sessions (legitimate:impostor ratio $\approx 3 : 1$). The methodological pipeline consisted of (i) model selection, (ii) user-independent validation, and (iii) performance refinement, as described below. Considering the moderate dataset imbalance and to mitigate potential bias toward the majority class during model training, we applied cost-sensitive class-weighted learning across all models that supported it (e.g., using `class_weight="balanced"`). For the tree-based models, we also treated class weighting as a tunable hyperparameter (including None vs. "balanced") and selected it via cross-validation within each training fold. We did not apply over- or under-sampling to preserve the natural frequency of authentication attempts and avoid altering the session distribution. All analyses were implemented in Python (v3.11.9) using scikit-learn (v1.7.2), XGBoost (v3.1.3), NumPy (v1.26.3), and pandas (v2.2.3).

4.1.1 Model selection. We evaluated six families of supervised classifiers (Table 3) to capture linear and nonlinear relationships among gaze metrics and to assess the generalizability of decision boundaries across unseen users. Ensemble-based methods were included for their ability to model complex interactions and provide feature importance analysis, while k NN and linear baselines served as reference points for geometric and parametric decision boundaries. All models were implemented in scikit-learn and trained using identical features and preprocessing steps.

4.1.2 Validation strategy. To assess generalization across unseen users and prevent identity leakage, we evaluated model performance following a Leave-One-User-Out (LOUO) cross-validation strategy. In each iteration, the data of one legitimate user and all corresponding impostor attempts targeting that legitimate user were held out for testing. This process was repeated for all users, and metrics were averaged across folds. Within each training fold, we performed internal scaling and hyperparameter tuning to avoid bias from test-user information leakage. We used the following metrics: (i) accuracy: proportion of correctly classified sessions overall; (ii) balanced accuracy: average of recall across both classes, mitigating class imbalance effects; (iii) F1 score: harmonic mean of precision and recall, reflecting classification balance; (iv) FAR (False Acceptance Rate): proportion of impostor attempts incorrectly classified as legitimate (high FAR means the system allows unauthorized users in, reducing security); (v) FRR (False Rejection Rate): proportion of legitimate users incorrectly rejected as impostors (high FRR means that the system does not allow legitimate users to login, reducing usability); and (vi) AUC (Area Under the Curve): area under the ROC (Receiver Operating Characteristic) curve, capturing discrimination power across thresholds. We note that we emphasize metrics robust to class imbalance and report class-specific error rates to support practical interpretation.

4.1.3 Performance refinement. To fine-tune model hyperparameters, reduce overfitting, and improve the balance between impostor detection (security) and legitimate acceptance (usability), we selected the top-performing models, and each model underwent targeted optimization using its

Table 3. Model families, representative models, and rationale for inclusion.

Family	Models	Description
Linear	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Logistic Regression – Linear SVM 	Establish baseline linear decision boundaries; interpretable weights capture direct relationships between gaze features and session role.
Kernel-based	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – RBF-SVM – Polynomial SVM 	Capture nonlinear boundaries in the gaze-feature space, accommodating curved or complex class separations.
Tree-based	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Decision Tree – Random Forest – Extra Trees – Gradient Boosting (GB) – XGBoost 	Model feature interactions and nonlinearities with built-in interpretability via feature importance; ensemble trees enhance robustness.
Instance-based	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) 	Classify sessions by local similarity in gaze-feature space; provides intuitive geometric perspective.
Probabilistic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Gaussian Naive Bayes (NB) 	Baseline generative model assuming conditional independence; useful for lightweight deployment or probabilistic calibration.
Neural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) 	Learns complex, hierarchical relationships across gaze metrics; serves as flexible nonlinear benchmark.

most influential parameters, while maintaining the same user-independent evaluation protocol. For each training set, an inner GroupKFold (3 splits) cross-validation was used for hyperparameter search, ensuring that no data from the test user appeared in the optimization process. Parameter selection aimed to maximize the average balanced accuracy and AUC within each training fold. Tree-based models were optimized using a grid search over the number of estimators (100–1000), maximum depth (4–32), and minimum split size (2–10). Boosting models were refined through GPU-accelerated Bayesian optimization (Optuna) over learning rate, maximum depth, subsampling ratios, and L_1/L_2 regularization parameters. The instance-based model was tuned over the number of neighbors ($\{3-15\}$) and distance metrics (Euclidean, Manhattan, Minkowski). We standardized all input features using a StandardScaler fitted on the training data of each fold, preventing information leakage. Model reproducibility was ensured through fixed random seeds (set to 42) and deterministic scikit-learn backends.

4.2 Results

4.2.1 Initial evaluation. Table 4 summarizes the mean performance of all evaluated models under LOUO validation. Overall, ensemble-based classifiers outperformed linear and kernel-based baselines, achieving higher balanced accuracy and AUC values. The top-performing models reached balanced accuracies around .83 and AUC values above .80, indicating moderate discriminative power

Table 4. Performance of all evaluated models under LOUO validation; bold values indicate the highest performance per metric.

Model	Accuracy	Balanced Acc.	F1 score	FAR	FRR	AUC
Logistic Regression	.775	.768	.859	.962	.000	.615
Linear SVM	.772	.765	.856	.987	.000	.532
RBF-SVM	.765	.757	.853	.929	.020	.770
Polynomial SVM	.772	.763	.856	.987	.000	.563
Decision Tree	.781	.780	.855	.442	.140	.764
Random Forest	.845	.840	.903	.487	.039	.802
Extra Trees	.839	.834	.897	.532	.039	.838
GB	.831	.826	.884	.468	.081	.809
XGBoost	.824	.819	.890	.468	.070	.787
kNN	.838	.833	.896	.538	.039	.803
Gaussian NB	.751	.744	.837	.897	.059	.520
MLP	.756	.749	.839	.763	.090	.771

under user-independent conditions. Performance variability across folds was low ($SD < .131$), suggesting stable generalization across users. Regarding the correct identification of legitimate users and impostors (i) Random Forest achieved rates of 96% and 51%, respectively; (ii) Extra Trees achieved rates of 96% and 47%, respectively; (iii) GB achieved rates of 92% and 53%, respectively; (iv) XGBoost achieved rates of 93% and 53%, respectively; (v) k NN achieved rates of 96% and 46%, respectively. Hence, if the primary objective is to enhance security (i.e., maximize impostor detection), boosting models such as GB and XGBoost are preferable, whereas Random Forest, Extra Trees, and k NN favor usability by minimizing false rejections of legitimate users. Regarding feature importance, the analysis based on impurity-based scores revealed a consistent dominance of temporal and spatial metrics. Measures of `mean_dwelling_time`, `std_dwelling_time`, and `gaze_efficiency`, along with fixation-based indicators, were consistently ranked among the most discriminative predictors. These were followed by entropy-based descriptors that capture the regularity and predictability of scanpath transitions. These results indicate that models primarily relied on temporal allocation and spatial search efficiency to distinguish legitimate from impostor behavior, confirming the RQ_1 finding that impostors exhibit slower, more exploratory gaze strategies during PIN entry.

4.2.2 Refinement loop. We further refined the top-performing models through targeted optimization to enhance discriminative performance and model stability. We focused on fine-tuning hyperparameters of the best classifiers while maintaining user-independent validation. The refinement of the k NN, Random Forest, and GB models resulted in performance comparable to their baseline configurations, with accuracy and AUC remaining within the same range, indicating that they were already well-calibrated and that optimization primarily enhanced model stability. In contrast, the Extra Trees model demonstrated improvement, increasing impostor detection from 47% to 51% and slightly raising the AUC while maintaining a high true acceptance rate for legitimate users ($\approx 95\%$), thereby achieving a better balance between security and usability. XGBoost demonstrated the most notable enhancement, with accuracy reaching .85 and a reduction in FRR to 4.7%. Table 5 summarizes the results. We note that under the stringent user-independent setting in which impostors enter the correct PIN, distinguishing between legitimate and impostor sessions is

Table 5. Performance of the refined models; bold values indicate the highest performance per metric.

Model	Accu- racy	Balanced Acc.	F1 score	FAR	FRR	AUC
Random Forest	.827 (-2%)	.823 (-2%)	.893 (-1%)	.487 (-)	.059 (+50%)	.820 (+2%)
Extra Trees	.836 (-)	.831 (-)	.898 (-)	.487 (-8%)	.050 (+28%)	.853 (+2%)
GB	.834 (-)	.829 (-)	.897 (+1%)	.487 (+4%)	.048 (-40%)	.811 (-)
XGBoost	.846 (+3%)	.842 (+3%)	.902 (+1%)	.471 (+1%)	.047 (-33%)	.838 (+6%)
kNN	.808 (-4%)	.804 (-3%)	.871 (-3%)	.530 (-2%)	.090 (+128%)	.761 (-5%)

inherently challenging; accordingly, we emphasize balanced accuracy, AUC, and FAR/FRR rather than overall accuracy for interpretation.

Finding 2: Tree-based models provide consistent, user-independent discrimination

Gaze-based features consistently distinguished legitimate from impostor authentication attempts under user-independent validation. Among evaluated classifiers, tree-based ensembles achieved balanced accuracies around .83 and AUC values above .80, indicating moderate yet stable discriminative power across unseen users. Their advantage stems from their ability to model nonlinear interactions among temporal and spatial gaze metrics, making them well-suited to capture individual variability in visual behavior during PIN entry. The refinement phase further improved cross-fold stability and slightly enhanced usability, with XGBoost achieving the best overall balance between security and usability.

5 RQ3 – Model calibration and security-usability balance

5.1 Methodology

Following the comparative evaluation in RQ_2 , *XGBoost* was selected as the top-performing model; RQ_3 therefore focuses on how this model can be calibrated to operate under different security–usability regimes that reflect realistic operational conditions. We note that the model is not intended to replace the primary PIN mechanism nor to function as a standalone blocking gate. Instead, it operates as an implicit second authentication factor that produces a behavioral risk signal during PIN entry, which can inform adaptive authentication policies (e.g., [Katsini et al. \[2026\]](#)).

5.1.1 Model configuration. The analyses in RQ_3 leverage the generalized hyperparameter configuration obtained during cross-validation in RQ_2 , which was re-applied to the full dataset to ensure consistency across experiments. The selected *XGBoost* model used a `learning_rate` of 0.121, balancing convergence speed and stability, and `n_estimators` of 404, providing sufficient boosting iterations for fine-grained discrimination of gaze-derived behavioral cues. The `max_depth` was set to approximately 6.8, defining a moderately complex tree structure capable of capturing non-linear feature interactions without overfitting. The `gamma = 0.346` parameter introduced a minimum loss reduction requirement before further node splitting, while `min_child_weight = 1.86` constrained leaf node formation by enforcing a minimum sample weight. The subsampling parameters `subsample = 0.804` and `colsample_bytree = 0.797` introduced controlled stochasticity by using approximately 80% of samples and features per tree, enhancing generalization through internal regularization. Finally, the L2 regularization term `reg_lambda = 2.280` further mitigated

overfitting by penalizing large weights. This configuration represents a moderately complex and well-regularized model that achieves a balance between expressiveness and stability. Although the relatively large number of trees increases computational cost during model retraining, no evidence of overfitting was observed during cross-validation.

5.1.2 Stability and generalization. To assess generalization beyond the training participants, all calibration analyses followed a LOUO validation protocol; the per-fold metrics (AUC, EER: Equal Error Rate) were aggregated across all users to quantify cross-user generalizability and calibration stability. Specifically, for each test fold, FAR, FRR, and TAR (True Acceptance Rate = $1 - \text{FRR}$) rates were computed at multiple thresholds, from which the AUC and EER were derived as measures of discriminative ability and calibration balance. The distribution of AUC and EER values across folds was then analyzed to identify consistency and variance in model performance.

5.1.3 Threshold calibration stability. To evaluate the consistency of optimal decision boundaries across users, we conducted per-user ROC analyses using the score distributions of legitimate and impostor samples. For each user, the threshold corresponding to EER was extracted as the point where $\text{FAR} \approx \text{FRR}$, representing the individualized calibration boundary. The resulting per-user thresholds were summarized by their mean, standard deviation, and range to quantify variability across the population.

5.1.4 Adaptive decision policies. To investigate how the global model could adapt to varying operational requirements, system-level trade-offs were analyzed through the ROC and DET (Detection Error Tradeoff) curves, sweeping the decision threshold across the full range of impostor probabilities. We identified and analyzed three representative operating modes: high-security, balanced, and high-usability modes.

5.2 Results

5.2.1 Stability and generalization. The model achieved consistent performance across folds (AUC $M = .838$, $SD = .118$), indicating robust transferability of gaze-based behavioral patterns to unseen participants. At the balanced operating point, EER was $M = .321$ ($SD = .066$), demonstrating that the model maintains reliable calibration between false acceptance and false rejection probabilities across users. The relatively low variability in both AUC and EER values suggests stable discriminative performance and decision boundaries, supporting the feasibility of applying a generalized calibration threshold in practical deployments.

5.2.2 Threshold calibration stability. Across all users, the optimal thresholds averaged $M = .417$ ($SD = .288$, range $[.014, .967]$). Although the mean threshold value lies near the mid-range of the classifier's probability outputs, the relatively broad dispersion indicates noticeable inter-user variability in the score required to balance false acceptances and rejections. This pattern suggests that while the global model generalizes well on average, individual users differ in their calibration boundaries, likely reflecting distinct gaze dynamics and contextual influences. As a result, a single global threshold may provide satisfactory overall performance, but user-specific or context-adaptive calibration could further enhance consistency and reliability across diverse XR users.

5.2.3 Adaptive decision policies. The ROC curve (Fig. 1b) translates model calibration into adaptive operational policies, with each point reflecting a distinct security–usability trade-off determined by the decision threshold. Instead of representing fixed access-control configurations, these operating points define different sensitivity levels of risk. By adjusting this threshold, the implicit second gaze-based factor modulates the extent to which gaze deviations influence subsequent system responses (e.g., step-up authentication, re-verification) by operating in different modes:

Fig. 1. (a) Spatial configuration of the XR PIN-entry interface, annotated with viewing distance, key dimensions, and inter-element spacing ($L = 10\text{cm}$); (b) ROC curve of the XGBoost classifier, highlighting the thresholds corresponding to the adaptive decision modes.

- **High-security mode (conservative risk threshold)** corresponds to a strict sensitivity setting in which even moderate gaze deviations increase the risk score. At $\text{FAR} = 1\%$, the model achieves $\text{FRR} = 67.3\%$ with a decision threshold of .778, while at $\text{FAR} = 5\%$, FRR decreases to 53.8% at a threshold of .614; in practical deployment, such conservative thresholds would trigger step-up verification mechanisms in high-stakes XR contexts, where elevated risk leads to escalation rather than immediate access denial.
- **Balanced mode (EER point)** corresponds to the equilibrium between security and usability, where false acceptance and false rejection rates converge; at the EER point ($\approx 26.7\%$), the system operates at a threshold of .168, providing balanced performance without favoring either dimension; this configuration serves as a neutral calibration reference rather than a prescriptive deployment setting.
- **High-usability mode (permissive risk threshold)** corresponds to a relaxed sensitivity setting in which only strong gaze anomalies increase the risk score. When $\text{FRR} = 1\%$, FAR rises to 84.2% with a threshold of .011, and at $\text{FRR} = 5\%$, FAR remains at 67.6% with a threshold of .026; in practical deployment, such permissive configurations would typically be combined with multi-attempt monitoring or additional contextual safeguards, ensuring that isolated anomalous sessions do not immediately determine final access decisions.

These operating modes should be interpreted as calibration boundaries rather than fixed deployment prescriptions. The gaze-based model produces a continuous behavioral risk score that can be integrated with policy-level mechanisms (e.g., escalation after repeated anomalies), enhancing PIN authentication without acting as an independent binary gate.

Finding 3: Calibrating gaze-based models enables adaptable balance between security and usability

The XGBoost model demonstrated stable and transferable calibration behavior, indicating that gaze-based models can flexibly adapt to diverse operational contexts. By adjusting the decision threshold, system operators can dynamically modulate the balance between strict security and user convenience, shifting from conservative risk thresholds appropriate for high-stakes contexts to permissive, low-FRR configurations optimized for usability. This

adaptability highlights the practical potential of gaze behavior as an implicit authentication factor: rather than a fixed classifier, it can serve as a tunable mechanism that aligns system behavior with situational risk and user needs, paving the way for context-aware, policy-driven authentication in XR. This flexibility reflects policy-level configuration of behavioral risk rather than standalone access-control decisions.

6 Discussion

6.1 Findings, implications, and lessons learned

This work explored how gaze behavior can serve as an implicit behavioral layer to enhance the security of PIN-based authentication in XR. While PINs remain one of the most ubiquitous and usable authentication mechanisms, they also introduce the risk of unauthorized access: anyone who knows the correct PIN can log in and access the protected account or service. Our study contributes to usable security research by demonstrating that gaze dynamics, captured unobtrusively during PIN authentication, encode measurable behavioral patterns that provide a continuous risk signal capable of differentiating legitimate from impostor sessions even when the correct PIN is entered. Rather than replacing conventional authentication mechanisms, our approach positions gaze as an implicit second factor that strengthens resilience against unauthorized use while preserving familiarity and usability.

Across the research questions, we identified three complementary insights. First, gaze behavior during PIN authentication reveals measurable differences between legitimate users and impostors, most notably in spatial efficiency and temporal attention; legitimate users displayed more direct scanpaths and shorter dwell times, whereas impostors engaged in slower, less efficient visual exploration, patterns that reflect increased cognitive uncertainty during PIN entry. This finding extends prior XR research on visual attention during interaction tasks, indicating that gaze behavior can be used as an authentication factor. Second, tree-based machine learning models, particularly ensemble methods, achieved consistent discrimination between legitimate and impostor sessions under user-independent validation. Their reliance on temporal and spatial metrics suggests that implicit gaze cues generalize across individuals when modeled through nonlinear decision boundaries. Third, calibrating the top-performing XGBoost model revealed that the gaze-based factor can flexibly adapt to different operational requirements, enabling explicit control over the trade-off between security (low false acceptance) and usability (low false rejection). This calibration capacity supports context-aware deployment strategies in XR, where situational demands range from high-security administrative access to casual consumer use.

Focusing on the theoretical implications, our work contributes to the growing discourse on usable security and behavioral modeling in immersive environments by reframing the role of gaze from a primary biometric identifier into an implicit layer that strengthens existing authentication mechanisms. Unlike prior research that suggests novel authentication mechanisms, often improving security at the cost of usability, our work focuses on complementing traditional methods such as PIN entry with an unobtrusive behavioral layer. This perspective extends current theories of multimodal authentication and behavioral biometrics by highlighting that gaze can serve as a continuous cue reflecting attention and familiarity. In this sense, gaze operates as a soft behavioral safeguard supporting the detection of anomalous access attempts even when explicit credentials are correct. Conceptually, the work bridges cognitive models of visual attention with frameworks of adaptive, human-centered authentication, advancing a view of security not as a replacement of user practices but as seamless reinforcement within XR interaction.

Regarding the practical implications, this work introduces an approach for enhancing existing authentication mechanisms in XR without disrupting user experience or requiring additional user effort. By operating as an implicit, passive layer, the gaze-based method continuously monitors behavioral consistency during PIN entry, enabling the detection of anomalous or elevated-risk sessions even when explicit credentials are correct. Notably, the model's adaptive calibration capability allows multiple stakeholders (e.g., end users, system developers, and service providers) to fine-tune the decision thresholds according to contextual requirements. Considering that context can affect authentication performance and user perceptions [Katsini et al. 2025; Noah et al. 2025], users may favor higher usability in low-risk everyday sessions, while developers or providers can enforce stricter configurations in security-critical contexts, achieving a dynamic balance through policy-level control. This adaptability supports a broader ecosystem perspective, where authentication sensitivity aligns with situational risk and the application domain. As gaze tracking becomes standard in XR hardware, the proposed approach offers a scalable path toward context-aware, privacy-preserving, and user-centered authentication systems that integrate seamlessly with established practices and infrastructures.

6.2 Limitations and future work

While the study provides promising evidence for the feasibility of gaze-based implicit authentication in XR, several limitations should be acknowledged: (i) the model showed inter-user variability in calibration thresholds, indicating that individual differences in gaze behavior limited the reliability of a single global decision boundary; (ii) gaze-based metrics may be sensitive to contextual factors such as lighting, headset positioning, and environmental conditions, thus potentially affecting robustness outside controlled settings; (iii) the study was limited to gaze data collected during 6-digit PIN entry in XR, which restricts generalization to other authentication mechanisms (e.g., alphanumeric passwords) and variations (e.g., 4-digit PIN authentication); (iv) the evaluation was cross-sectional, providing limited evidence of how gaze-based behavioral patterns evolve or stabilize over time; (v) privacy and user perception aspects of gaze-based implicit authentication were not investigated, leaving open questions regarding acceptability and ethical deployment.

Building on the aforementioned limitations, future research should seek methodological and design extensions to strengthen generalizability, robustness, and ethical integration. Directions include: (i) implementation of adaptive, user-specific calibration mechanisms using incremental or transfer learning to mitigate inter-user variability; (ii) consideration of diverse contextual and environmental factors in model training to enhance robustness under real-world XR conditions; (iii) extension to other user authentication mechanisms and variations of PIN authentication; (iv) implementation of longitudinal experiments assessing the temporal stability of gaze-based features and explore online retraining strategies for sustained accuracy; (v) integration of privacy-by-design principles and examination of user trust, consent, and transparency to ensure ethical and user-acceptable adoption.

7 Conclusion

Our work demonstrated that gaze dynamics can serve as an implicit factor to enhance PIN-based authentication in XR environments. Legitimate users and impostors showed systematically different patterns of visual attention, revealing behavioral cues that can be modeled to identify unauthorized access. Beyond classification accuracy, the proposed approach enables adaptive calibration, allowing systems to balance security and usability according to situational needs. Moreover, the proposed method operates unobtrusively, requiring no additional user action or hardware beyond the built-in gaze tracking capabilities of current XR headsets. Our findings contribute to the growing field of behavioral authentication by showing how natural gaze behavior reflects both identity and

intent during interaction. Future work should extend this approach across multiple mechanisms and variations, assess long-term behavioral stability, and integrate privacy-by-design principles to ensure the ethical and user-centered deployment of gaze-based enhancements in immersive environments.

Privacy and ethics statement

This research examines gaze behavior as an implicit factor in authentication, with a focus on privacy, fairness, and responsible innovation. All data were anonymized and handled in accordance with the ethical guidelines and research procedures of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki. No personally identifiable information was collected. The study was designed to minimize societal risks and to support privacy-preserving use of gaze-based authentication technologies.

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